

IN-SITU SYNTHESIZED MAGNESIUM MATRIX COMPOSITES

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Shanghai, 200030, P.R.China*T.X. Fan (txfan@sjtu.edu.cn)**Keywords:** *In-situ synthesized, Damping capacity, Compression deformation***1 Introduction**

In the past 20 years, magnesium matrix composites have progressed from a primary laboratory enterprise with minor commercial significance to a diverse and robust class of materials the lowest density among all metallic constructional materials [1]. Besides, they have excellent specific strength, high damping capacity and recycling capability. Therefore, magnesium matrix composites are excellent substitutes for light structure materials, and have great potential in automotive, high performance defense and aerospace applications. However, the use of magnesium alloys has been limited because of the poor mechanical properties and low elastic modulus prevents its wide applications [2]. To overcome the inherent problems, in situ technique has been investigated since it exhibits the finer reinforcement better distribution and the cleaner reinforcement–matrix interface than ex situ one. Among widely used reinforcements, TiC ceramic particles possess many desirable properties [3]. In present work, molten magnesium alloy was spontaneously infiltrated into Al–Ti–C preforms, simultaneously the in situ reaction happened and TiC particles were formed in the liquid of magnesium alloy.

2. Experimental

The preforms were made from commercial powders of Ti, Al and C and mixed (at molar ratio of Ti/C = 1:1 with 30 wt.% Al) in a ball mill filled with argon gas for 1 h and then pressed into preforms ($\phi 30\text{mm} \times 10\text{ mm}$). Commercial AZ91D magnesium alloy was chosen with nominal chemical composition Mg–9.1Al–0.8Zn–0.2Mn (wt.%). The compacted preforms were placed at the bottom of a steel crucible with commercial AZ91D magnesium alloys on it. The added amount of Al–Ti–C preforms was changed to obtain different volume fraction of TiC reinforced magnesium matrix composites. The

preforms and magnesium alloys were heated to 750 °C under the protection of argon and held for about 30 min. After that, the temperature was reduced slowly to the mushy zone between 555 °C and 570 °C. The molten magnesium alloy was stirred with a graphite stirrer for 30 min to assist the dispersion of the particles. The melts were then heated to 750 °C and cast into steel mould preheated to 250 °C.

Damping capacity was measured on a Dynamic Mechanical Analysis (IDMA2980) with dimensions of 40mm×4mm×1mm. The measurement conditions were as follows: the frequency of approximately 0.1–15 Hz, the strain amplitude from 10^{-5} to 10^{-3} and temperature from room temperature to 350°C. Cylindrical specimens 8mm in diameter and 12mm in height were used for compression tests. The compressive deformation behaviors were carried out at room temperature (25°C), 100, 150 and 200°C with strain rate of 1, 10^{-1} , 10^{-2} and 10^{-3} s⁻¹ on Gleeble-3500 machine, respectively

3 Results and Discussion**3.1 Damping capacity**

The damping capacities of AZ91D alloy and composites, as a function of temperature are shown in Fig. 1. It can be seen the damping capacities rise with increasing temperature. At low temperature (from room temperature to 200 °C), damping capacities of AZ91D alloy and TiC/AZ91D composites increased slowly with ascending temperature. As it is mentioned above, one of the possible dominant damping mechanisms for TiC/AZ91D composites at relatively low temperature is dislocation damping. When the temperature is less than 200 °C, damping capacities of AZ91D alloy and 1 vol% TiC/AZ91D composite show no obvious difference. It is due to the adding content of TiC particles does not introduce enough dislocation to improve damping capacities.

Fig.1 Damping capacities versus temperature for AZ91D alloy and TiC/AZ91D composites with testing frequency of 0.1 Hz .

Damping capacities of 3 vol% TiC/AZ91D and 5 vol% TiC/AZ91D composites are higher than that of AZ91D alloy below 200 °C, which shows that the increase of reinforcement is beneficial to the improvement of damping capacities of composites [3].

3.2 Compressive deformation behaviors

The compression properties of AZ91D alloy and 3 vol% TiC/AZ91D composites were investigated at temperatures ranging from room temperature (25°C) to 200 °C and strain rates from 10^{-3} to 1 s^{-1} . Typically stress-strain curves obtained at different temperatures are shown in Fig.2 (a), (b). The results shown that it takes more stress to reach the maximum strain for the introduction of TiC. And

the maximum strain tends to shift towards the lower value for the existence of TiC. It manifests that the

Fig.2 The compression deformation behavior of (a) AZ91D alloy at 1 s^{-1} , (b) 3 vol% TiC/AZ91D composites at 1 s^{-1} .

compression resistance of TiC/AZ91D composites is enhanced for importing the TiC particles [4].

4 Conclusions

Molten magnesium was spontaneously infiltrated into Ti-C preforms, simultaneously the in situ reaction happened and TiC particles were formed in the liquid of magnesium alloy. The as-cast microstructure revealed the distribution of reinforcements was nearly uniform in the matrix. An increase in damping capacities of TiC/AZ91D composites can be attributed to the dislocation damping mechanism at room temperature. At elevated temperatures, interface damping is a new contributor to the increase of damping capacity. With the addition of TiC particles, TiC/AZ91D composites can effectively improve compressive properties of magnesium matrix at testing temperature interval.

Reference

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Materials Transactions, Vol. 49, No. 11, pp. 2686 to 2691,
2008.